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Progress in Physics (105)

Structural Biology and Interaction Analysis in Drug Discovery.

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Molecular biology studies the selective, spatial and timely recognition of molecules in cells. Evolution has tuned molecular recognition to orchestrate replication and adaption in biology. Only few elements are shaping biological matter, but the diversity and complexity of the resulting particle space is fantastically complex.

The challenge

A drug molecule is a particle that exposes a distinct recognition surface, engineered to take selective therapeutic action in an environment crowded with comparably composed matter. Different therapeutic modalities enable this. Immunotherapies are based upon humanized recombinant antibodies, antisense oligonucleotides and gene therapies modulate genes associated with diseases. The tablet is an oral dosage form, condensing a small molecule in a stable crystal structure. This soft matter solid state is required to match a reasonable dissolution profile and an appropriate shelf life stability. Once dissolved, the drug molecule must withstand a digestive bio-chemical environment with an acceptable drug metabolism. All drug molecules are exposed to body compartments and the immune system; they have to pass biological barriers and organs, a cell membrane, or the brain-blood barrier, to finally reach the anticipated target destination at a free and pharmacologically relevant concentration. The physical, chemical, and physiological information stored in a small molecule has to match a delicate and complex drug property profile in order to become a 'true drug'. This profile covers a multitude of independent aspects. Most importantly, the drug molecule has to be safe, and the processes to manufacture medicines require it to meet the highest quality standards.

The experimental approach

Target based drug discovery of small molecules follows a hierarchically organized funnel approach (Figure 1). It is experimental and computational guided by scientifically generated data, as well as the experiences collected over many decades. The first step of the discovery workflow has to satisfy the fundamental necessity to identify random chemical matter which can principally engage with the selected target. High-throughput screening reveals the engagement likelihood of any given library member with the anticipated target, resulting in a series of screening hits. These hits are

Figure 1: The funnel of small molecule drug discovery process leading to clinical candidate compounds.

structurally classified based upon repetitive structural motifs, and wider physicochemical properties. An alternative method which enables to screen the engagement of billions of molecules with a given target is the DNA-Encoded-Library-Technology (DEL). In addition to screens with synthesized molecules, in-silicon screens based upon prior structural information and virtual libraries are being employed as well. Often, different screening tools complement each other and feed the wider aim to generate a meaningful and rich series of chemically diverse starting points in a Lead Identification phase. The subsequent Lead Optimization phase merges structural motifs and novel chemical design ideas to consequently improve the compound properties into classes of potent lead structures, from which a clinical lead series and finally the clinical candidate are selected. These in-vitro experiments are complemented by cellular experiments and in-vivo studies to verify the mechanism of action of how the compound interacts with the drug target and to explore the wanted potential clinical mode of action of that mechanism. Overall the complexity of the general discovery challenge is smaller, if the selectivity, affinity and activity of the compound becomes large. Together these parameters define part of the potency of a compound. A general reduction of the required dose or the drug exposition at the target site most efficiently reduces undesired properties, all those which are concentration dependent, such as off-target effects, solubility or a poor membrane permeability. Structural knowledge in combination with biophysical interaction data provide an experimental foundation to design and improve molecules. Therefore, understanding this experimental foundation will help simplifying and accelerating the iterative optimization process of molecules with the chance to deliver highly potent and well-tolerated medicines.

Surface Plasmon Resonance, invented decades ago, is most established to determine the dissociation constants and binding kinetics of drug-target complexes with high throughput. Structure determination pipelines are applied in the entire pharmaceutical industry. They are based upon protein x-ray crystallography and cryogenic transmission electron microscopy (cryoTEM). Together these methods are the current technical standard to guide medical chemists and enable rational drug design.

The experimental limitation of the approach

The workflows, the throughput, the automation and analysis pipelines towards guiding structure determination and interaction analysis are continuously refined globally and across the pharmaceutical industry. Decades of broad and in-depth drug discovery have generated a wealth of structural information and interaction insights. Fundamentally, this knowledge space is sufficiently closed to predict structural models of proteins with high confidence, by the knowledge of the target sequence. The engagement of synthetic small molecule binders is challenging to predict.

The experimental approaches, as well as the in-silicon predictions, are constrained by the fact that the entire available information is gathered on recombinant proteins. Our structural and biophysical knowledge is limited to targets which can be expressed at the liter scale, to be isolated and purified in the milligram scale and with suitable homogeneity. The interaction analysis of binders requires a clean buffer environment, and the protein target space that satisfies this method's immanent needs has been explored in depth.

A novel discovery space could be unlocked, if rational drug design would be amendable to endogenous drug-protein complexes, supramolecular assemblies, or particles which are simply too vulnerable to be isolated with classical biochemistry in sufficient yields.

Innovative technologies are needed

Analytically, it is a challenge to measure the biophysical interaction of molecules in an environment crowded with biological matter, because selective recognition and non-specific interactions cannot be sufficiently distinguished. Physically, the formation of a drug-target complex generates a *de novo* particle which occupies a constantly larger volume than the target or the binder by themselves. Together, they form a changed mass and the optical properties are being changed. These local concentration modulations are minute and not reliable to quantify in situations where interaction noise is present due to non-specific interactions and thermal diffusion. The masking or shielding of the recognizing surfaces by non-specific interactions reduces the likelihood of a compound to engage. The affinity-selectivity ranking made under artificial constraints can be misleading, in some cases. New innovative approaches are reaching our horizon and attention, they manage targets to be studied in cell lysate and body fluids.

Focal Molography, an optical diffractive biosensor

Focal Molography orchestrates and sorts the binding activity of millions of individual molecules into a surface pattern acting as a 'two dimensional diffractive lens', the 'molecular hologram' or mologram (Figure 2). The laser light which passes through the lens becomes detectable in a focal spot. The light in the spot is a holographic signal created from millions of individual binding events in the mologram. The trick is that the mologram orchestrates selective recognition and non-selective interactions of molecules coherently in space. Through this key principle, unspecific or random binding events are suppressed and do not contribute to the

signal being measured in the focal spot, and the measurement applies the spatial lock-in amplification principle in an analogous manner [1,2].

Experimental data generated with Focal Molography are astonishing. For instance dissociation constants in the single-digit nanomolar concentration range can be reliably calculated from real time binding curves gathered in cell lysates. Peptides, which are conjugated to the mologram are selectively recognizing the protein target, at minute analytical concentrations. Multiplexed real-time binding curves were collected in serum and human-derived body fluids. Focal Molography unlocks a novel target opportunity space under cellular background conditions and biophysical interaction analysis of compounds with endogenous proteins.

CryoWriter, a microfluidic robot for structure determination with cryoTEM

Interaction analysis without structural knowledge of the drug-target complex is insufficient to guide medical chemists through an informed drug molecule optimization process. Technically, one million particle micrographs are enough to reconstruct a protein structure, large scale expression and purification cycles are not mandatory to feed a cryoTEM structure determination pipeline. The particles require to be embedded in an ultrathin amorphously-vitrified water film in random distributions and orientations. The preparation of suitable thin films is a preparative challenge, and time-wise, a bottleneck of the structure determination workflow, even though if proteins are available in large amounts and in good quality.

The cryoWriter is an innovation of the Thomas Braun Laboratory at the Biozentrum of the University of Basel and is currently being developed by a company in Basel. It matured into a versatile-modular, microfluidic-automated, biochemical laboratory (Figure 3). The environmental control and a multitude of sensory feedbacks enable the genera-

Figure 2: Diffraction Optical Biosensor. Dark Field Illumination (top left); coherent laser light is coupled into a planar waveguide on a sensor chip. The light passes the diffractive lens, the mologram (top right). The mologram is a periodic grating of selective recognition elements in the ridges, and mass matched reference elements in the grooves. Analyte molecules in a biological liquid have a larger likelihood to be captured by the ridges, because of the higher affinity of selective recognition elements. Analyte binding leads to a mass density modulation which is related with the periodicity of the grating (bottom right). Light diffracted by the ridges interferes with the light diffracted by the grooves; the ridges and grooves are two interfering gratings. The diffracted light intensity is detected at the focal spot of the mologram (bottom left), and is related to the coherent mass density modulation on the mologram.

Figure 3: cryoWriter, a microfluidic laboratory to prepare grids with nanoliter aliquots for structure determination with cryoTEM.

tion of promising samples for electron microscopy in a novel way. A key element is the tinny nozzle, this can be freely moved and positioned with micrometer accuracy in space. Nanoliters of liquids are pipetted with picoliters accuracy, from different well-plates to a sample incubator. A counterpart is the tweezer which manages the automated delivery of sample supports. These supports are called grids, and this tweezer manages its transport through different destinations of the cryoEM sample preparation workflow; to the plasma chamber, and to the launch pad, where thin films are deposited to be plunge-vitrified in liquid ethane. This launch pad is controlled to a temperature close to the dew point, and in our hands the robot delivers suitable grids from minute aliquots with accuracy and repeatability. A modular software orchestrates the interplay of these modular devices, thus that a multitude of operation workflows and conditions can be creatively explored in a short time.

Beyond enabling suitable grids for structure determination in a much shorter time, the robot is appealing because it is compatible with a magnetic bead purification device, which already enabled solving the structure of the endogenous human proteasome from 1 microliter of a cell lysate [3].

The combination of breakthrough technologies can reveal novel mechanistic insights into molecular recognition processes as they underlie cellular processes and diseases. Interaction data gathered with Focal Molography can be complemented with structural data gathered with cryoTEM. Magnetic bead purification with verified high affinity binders can directly be used to trap their corresponding target from microliter aliquots using the cryoWriter. The methods enlighten a novel experimental drug discovery space, molecular recognition cascades in molecular biology, and beyond applications in biomarker discovery, diagnostics or even real-time monitoring of biotechnological processes.

Collaboration towards novel technological breakthroughs

Innovative technologies have the chance to reach a transformative impact if fueled by the long-term commitment and passion of scientists across different disciplines and institutions. All starts with an invention; Dr. Christof Fattinger (Focal Molography) and Dr. Thomas Braun (cryoWriter). An academic home for Focal Molography was found in the groups of Prof. Dr. Janos Vörös and Prof. Dr. Petra Dittrich at the ETHZ, and the group of Dr. Thomas Braun at the Biozentrum of the University Basel. The development of a product prototype required the focus and motivated the foundation of start-ups; the lino Biotech AG and the cryoWrite® AG. It requires the laboratory infrastructure, experts and applicants in academia and industry to transform novel technology developments into robust data which enable the discovery of innovative molecules and novel therapies.

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The presentations of Dr. Andreas Frutiger¹ and Dr. Luca Rima² in the *Biophysics and Soft Matter* session at the SPS Annual Meeting 2024 provide further information.

¹ <https://indico.cern.ch/event/1382917/contributions/6028698/>

² <https://indico.cern.ch/event/1382917/contributions/6028727/>